

Conceptualization and Scalable Execution of Big Data Workflows Using Domain-Specific Languages and Software Containers

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Abstract

Big Data processing, especially with the increasing proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies and convergence of IoT, edge and cloud computing technologies, involves handling massive and complex data sets on heterogeneous resources and incorporating different tools, frameworks, and processes to help organizations make sense of their data collected from various sources. This set of operations, referred to as Big Data workflows, requires taking advantage of Cloud infrastructures' elasticity for scalability. In this article, we present the design and prototype implementation of a Big Data workflow approach based on the use of software container technologies, message-oriented middleware (MOM), and a domain-specific language (DSL) to enable highly scalable workflow execution and abstract workflow definition. We demonstrate our system in a use case and a set of experiments that show the practical applicability of the proposed approach for the specification and scalable execution of Big Data workflows. Furthermore, we compare our proposed approach's scalability with that of Argo Workflows – one of the most prominent tools in the area of Big Data workflows – and provide a qualitative evaluation of the proposed DSL and overall approach with respect to the existing literature.

Keywords: Big Data workflows, Internet of Things, Domain-specific languages, Software containers

1. Introduction

Massive amounts of data is being generated especially with the rise of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies creating new value creation opportunities through Big Data analysis. Accordingly, Big Data analysis has been a driving factor in revolutionizing major sectors, such as mobile services, finance, and scientific research. *Big Data workflows* are composed of multiple orchestrated steps, such as workflow activities that perform various data analytical tasks. They are different from business and scientific workflows since they are dynamic, process heterogeneous data, and are executed in parallel instead of a sequential set of scientific operators [1]. Although many organizations recognize the significance of Big Data analysis, they still face critical challenges when implementing data analytics into their process [2]. Firstly, multiple experts, ranging from technical to domain experts, need to be involved in specifying such complex workflows. Secondly, given the fact that IoT, Edge and Cloud technologies converge towards a computing continuum, workflow steps need to be mapped dynamically to heterogeneous computing and storage resources to ensure scalability [3, 4]. Providing a scalable, general-purpose solution for Big Data workflows that a broad audience can use is an open research issue [2, 4].

The challenges in devising an applicable generalized solution come from the fact that bottlenecks can occur on an individual workflow step level – for example, when the throughput of one step is lower than the others. Thus, scaling up the entire workflow does not address the scalability issues and needs to be done on the individual step level. This issue becomes worse by the fact that scalability needs to be organized and orchestrated over heterogeneous

18 computing resources. Furthermore, scaling up individual steps introduces race conditions between step instances
19 that attempt to process the same piece of data simultaneously. Another major challenge is achieving usability by
20 multiple stakeholders as most Big Data processing solutions are focused on ad-hoc processing models that only trained
21 professionals can use. However, organizations typically operate on specific software stacks, and getting experts in Big
22 Data technology can introduce costs that are not affordable or practical. Even if an organization has the necessary
23 technical personnel, data workflow steps pertain to specific domain-dependent knowledge, which is possessed by the
24 domain experts rather than the data scientists who set up the data workflows. In this respect, this work aims to provide
25 an approach that allows:

- 26 (a) conceptualization of Big Data workflows using a domain-specific language (DSL) to support the high-level
27 definition of complex data processing across multiple types of parameters, inputs, and outputs; and
- 28 (b) scalable execution of Big Data workflows using software container technologies and message-oriented middle-
29 ware solutions.

30 In this article, we present the design and implementation of a Big Data workflow approach based on the use of
31 software container technologies, message-oriented middleware (MOM), and a DSL to enable highly scalable workflow
32 execution and abstract workflow definition [5]. Our design allows for scaling up on the level of individual workflow
33 steps on top of heterogeneous infrastructures while avoiding race conditions through a system of inter- and intra-
34 step coordination. Furthermore, our container-based approach allows for the separation of concerns between the
35 stakeholders by providing a flexible means of injecting domain-specific code involving any programming language
36 and enabling the definition of workflows on a high level (i.e., without the step-specific code). Finally, the DSL
37 allows easy specification of Big Data workflows by abstracting low-level technical aspects. We demonstrate our
38 approach’s applicability by implementing a prototype based on a real-world data workflow and multiple experiments
39 showing satisfactory performance. Furthermore, a set of comparative experiments with Argo Workflows shows better
40 performance due to concurrent workflow execution. A qualitative evaluation of the overall approach and the DSL
41 with respect to the existing literature presents our approach’s benefits. This article extends our previous work in [5]
42 by providing (i) more insights and explanations about the motivation, approach and solution details, (ii) an extended
43 presentation and analysis of the related work, (iii) an elaborate account and analysis of the requirements for enabling
44 Big Data workflows on the Computing Continuum, (iv) a qualitative evaluation and discussion of the proposed DSL,
45 and (v) a set of examples of real-life use cases of the approach.

46 The rest of the article is organised as follows. Section 2 sets the background, while Section 3 discusses related
47 work. Section 4 describes the requirements and Section 5 presents the proposed approach. Section 6 discusses our
48 proof-of-concept implementation based on the proposed design, Section 7 provides an evaluation, and, finally Section
49 8 concludes the article and discusses possible future work.

50 **2. Background**

51 In this section we briefly introduce technological background relevant in the context of scalable Big Data work-
52 flows execution.

53 *2.1. Big Data Workflows*

54 A Big Data workflow is the computerized modeling and automation of a process consisting of multiple orches-
55 trated steps that perform various data analysis tasks [6]. In practice, most Big Data workflows are usually represented
56 by a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) [7]. Various processing models can be applied for parallelizing data process-
57 ing known as workflow data patterns [8]. In this context, Pipe and Filter (P&F) is a relevant architectural design to
58 decompose a larger processing task into a series of smaller, separate processing steps (filters) that are connected by
59 channels (pipes) [9]. The filters can then be integrated into a workflow, whereby each filter receives and sends data
60 in a standardized way, thus implementing the “shared data passed by reference” pattern [8]. This pattern, given that
61 different steps are loosely coupled, enables scalability at the workflow step level, but introduces the issue of handling
62 concurrency control.

63 2.2. Message-oriented Middleware

64 Achieving race-condition-free consistency and concurrency for scaling the homogeneous Big Data workflow steps
65 requires using a synchronization mechanism across the different step instances. One approach for addressing such
66 synchronization issues is to use Message-Oriented Middleware (MOM). MOM provides an infrastructure for loosely-
67 coupled and asynchronous inter-process communication using messaging capabilities [10]. In a system integrated
68 using MOM, a client can send messages to and receive from the other clients of the messaging system (without losses
69 or message duplication) in a race-condition-free way through the use of a message queue. Thus, in the context of Big
70 Data workflows, the middleware can act as a medium for communication, whereby step instances coordinate passing
71 intermediate results through sending/receiving messages in MOM queues.

72 2.3. Container Technology

73 A container is a packaged, standalone, deployable collection of program elements [11]. Containers provide an
74 isolated virtual environment and include all the required dependencies of the provisioned tools. Docker is one of
75 the most well-known platforms for organizing solutions based on container technologies. When executing multiple
76 containers, a container orchestration system can manage their deployment, scaling, and networking. In particular,
77 container technology is useful for deploying distributed scalable applications (such as Big Data workflows), as it pro-
78 vides transparent means for infrastructure management and easy scalability of individual application sub-components.
79 Orchestration tools use a configuration file to define container images, network, and related deployment schemes of
80 an application.

81 2.4. Domain-Specific Languages

82 DSLs are programming languages or specification languages that target a specific problem domain. DSLs are
83 small, descriptive, and contain only the details needed for the desired domain. In general, there are two types of
84 DSLs: internal and external [12]. An internal DSL is a specific form of Application Programming Interface (API) in
85 a host general-purpose language (GPL). In contrast, an external DSL is a language that is parsed independently of the
86 host GPL. Unlike GPLs, DSLs are limited in scope and cannot cover all aspects of a given problem. However, they are
87 more effective than GPLs in providing expressiveness at the cost of generality. DSLs offer better domain-specificity
88 and significantly improve collaboration between domain experts and developers [13].

89 3. Related Work

90 In this section, related work is presented in terms of related scientific literature and commercial and non-commercial
91 software tools. Aspects such as workflow resource scheduling and others, as described in [4, 14], are complementary
92 to our approach as the described concept uses container orchestration systems to specify them.

93 3.1. Related Software Tools

94 There is a large variety of Big Data workflow solutions that share similar design principles while fulfilling the
95 needs of various groups of users and use cases. We carried out a comparative analysis of the most promising workflow
96 tools (chosen based on their mass user base and relevance), including Pachyderm¹, Apache Airflow², Snakemake³,
97 Apache NiFi⁴, Node-RED⁵, Argo Workflows⁶, NextFlow⁷, and Conductor⁸. An overview of the comparison is pre-
98 sented in Table 1 with respect to workflow type, usability for non-technical experts, run time container support, and
99 generality of the solution.

¹<https://www.pachyderm.com>

²<https://airflow.apache.org>

³<https://snakemake.readthedocs.io>

⁴<https://nifi.apache.org>

⁵<https://nodered.org>

⁶<https://argoproj.github.io/argo>

⁷<https://www.nextflow.io>

⁸<https://netflix.github.io/conductor>

Table 1: Comparison matrix for tools supporting Big Data workflows.

Tool name	Workflow type	Usability	Container support	Generic solution
Airflow	General-purpose	Difficult	Docker	Yes
Argo	General-purpose	Difficult	Docker	Yes
Conductor	General-purpose	Difficult	No	Yes
Nextflow	Scientific	Medium	Docker	No
NiFi	General-purpose	Medium	No	No
Node-RED	General-purpose	Medium	No	No
Snakemake	General-purpose	Medium	Docker	Yes
Pachyderm	General-purpose	Difficult	Docker	No
<i>Our approach</i>	<i>General-purpose</i>	<i>Easy</i>	<i>Docker</i>	<i>Yes</i>

100 We consider two main types of workflows - *scientific* and *general-purpose*. *Scientific* workflow approaches are
101 built to be applied in homogeneous infrastructures, such as High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters, where
102 resources are shared between multiple workflows and dedicated algorithms are used to optimise job scheduling and
103 resource allocation. On the other hand, *general-purpose* workflow tools are applicable in varying domains/scenarios
104 and can be executed in heterogeneous computing infrastructures. In terms of *usability* for non-technical experts, we
105 consider three levels of support - *easy*, *medium*, and *difficult*. We regard approaches that provide a dedicated DSL/UI
106 that caters to domain experts as *easy*. If the approach requires the use of coding of the Big Data workflows in a
107 specific programming language, we consider the approach of *medium* usability. On the other hand, if the approach
108 requires coding and the use of approach-specific concepts and libraries in order to declare a workflow, we consider
109 the approach to be *hard* in terms of usability to non-technical experts. With respect to *container support*, we classify
110 the approaches on whether or not they support the use of container technologies (e.g., Docker) for encapsulating the
111 entire Big Data workflow or individual steps. We note that although some of the tools, such as Apache NiFi, are
112 packaged and deployable using container technology⁹, but we do not consider them to provide *container support*.
113 Finally, we consider the solutions in terms of whether or not they are generic or catered for a specific vertical domain
114 of knowledge. Thereby, we regard approaches that are applicable in any vertical domain as *generic* and vice versa.

115 Argo Workflows natively supports containers in workflows by implementing each step as a container. The work-
116 flow definition and automation are done by YAML templates based on a custom DSL¹⁰. The steps can be arranged
117 either sequentially or in a DAG, making it possible to orchestrate and parallelize jobs. However, Argo Workflows
118 does not have a middleware solution to handle inter-step communication, which may result in step instances running
119 into race conditions when scaled horizontally. Additionally, individual steps cannot be scaled up in order to increase
120 the workflow throughput (although they can be run in parallel).

121 Nextflow is a workflow framework based on the dataflow paradigm [15]. It uses a declarative processing model to
122 execute parallel tasks and supports step-level scalability. Nextflow has built-in support for container technologies and
123 the communication among processes is handled using channels, and asynchronous First-In-First-Out (FIFO) queues
124 preventing race conditions. Nextflow provides a custom DSL to write complex workflows, which is an extension
125 to Apache Groovy¹¹. Nextflow does not provide a clear separation of concerns between workflow definition and
126 implementation and relies on a specific software stack (through the DSL) for workflow step implementation.

127 Apache Airflow is a platform for the creation, scheduling, and monitoring of data workflows. Python scripts are
128 used to describe DAG structured workflows. Airflow has a scheduler that executes workflows on a set of workers, but
129 it lacks a mechanism to avoid race-conditions when scaled. Airflow has a rich user interface support allowing users
130 to visualize workflows and monitor their execution. The workflow definition is done via programming. Pachyderm is
131 a tool for managing data workflow and related input/output data that results in all the data workflows' reproducibility
132 and scalability. Pachyderm is based on Docker and Kubernetes, and provides advanced features such as pluralisation
133 and incremental processing. Users need technical knowledge to define workflows.

⁹<https://hub.docker.com/r/apache/nifi>

¹⁰<https://argoproj.github.io/argo-workflows/fields/>

¹¹<https://groovy-lang.org/>

134 Snakemake is a workflow system in which workflows are defined in terms of rules presenting the input-output
135 conversion of files. Determining dependencies between rules, Snakemake automatically forms parallelizable DAG
136 workflows. It provides a concise and readable DSL, an extension of Python programming language, for defining rules
137 and workflow specific properties. It was initially developed for scalable workflows in bioinformatics. Apache NiFi
138 is a project of Apache Software Foundations that allows automation of data flow between systems. It is based on
139 a flow-based programming model for building scalable data workflows. Although it comes with a user interface, it
140 requires technical knowledge to design workflows.

141 Node-RED is another flow-based programming workflow tool that is built based on Node.js run-time. It follows
142 the event-driven and non-blocking model. It provides a Web-based visual editor for designing workflows, but it still
143 requires technical knowledge from the user. Even though Node-RED was initially designed for Internet-of-Things
144 (IoT) applications, it has evolved to develop various applications. Conductor is a workflow orchestration engine by
145 Netflix that allows creating microservice-based business and process workflows. Workflows are composed of tasks
146 that are executed by remote workers. A JSON-based DSL is used to define workflows.

147 3.2. Related Studies

148 Many efforts have been made to use containers to address the challenges of scalability, resource provisioning,
149 scheduling, orchestration, and data management of data workflows. Authors in [16] propose an approach for de-
150 composing scientific workflows into micro-units that are containerized and contain sub-workflows that communicate
151 through streaming middleware among each other and other applications and devices. This approach is specific to the
152 domain of digital twins and addresses the job dependency, job scheduling, and streaming support issues, but does not
153 provide means of independent scaling of steps and is domain-specific.

154 Another set of approaches relies on the use of container technology to deploy workers that execute jobs. Authors
155 in [7] use Docker to deploy a software stack to homogenize the environment where tasks are run. However, their
156 approach has limitations on the number of workflow step containers deployed on a single host and does not support
157 long-running tasks (i.e., containers are shut down after executing). The approach in [17] uses containers to encapsulate
158 workers that contain the workflow engine and execution environment but is applicable only in the context of
159 workflows expressed in a specific stream-based dataflow DSL [18], which reduces applicability for general-purpose
160 data workflows.

161 Another set of data workflow implementations in the area of HPC are built on top of the Shifter [19] framework.
162 Authors in [20] use the framework to distribute jobs and entire workflows (encapsulated in a single container) over
163 an HPC cluster. This approach does not support individual steps' scalability but views data workflows as entire units
164 of work. Authors in [21] rely on Shifter for defining virtual HPC clusters to run jobs. Thereby, containers are used
165 for creating worker nodes with the necessary HPC functionality and for managing the jobs, but their approach is not
166 applicable for general-purpose data workflows.

167 One approach that comes close to the one described in this paper is presented in [1], whereby containers are used
168 to wrap individual steps. The framework uses a TOSCA [22] to describe both the deployment and workflow steps,
169 which containers can implement. However, the framework does not support dynamic workflows - tasks are executed
170 in a sequential manner, whereby a task must finish for next to be deployed, which makes the approach not suitable for
171 long-running workflows.

172 Finally, authors in [23] use Cloud orchestration for deploying distributed workflows in a similar manner as the one
173 described here, although containers are not supported. However, the approach does not support run-time scalability
174 and relies on the step definition to manage the input and output between the steps. Furthermore, the approach uses a
175 DSL that provides no clear separation of concerns between the design- and run-time phases of data workflows.

176 4. Requirements

177 Commonly used data processing frameworks (such as Spark, Flink, Beam) are designed with ad-hoc process-
178 ing models that technical experts on specific technology stacks can only use. The focus is on the programming and
179 run-time aspects of workflows than the actual definition of workflows themselves. Even though some solutions, as dis-
180 cussed in related work, have demonstrated defining and executing Big Data workflows, they do not cater to the needs
181 of domain experts. Solutions like Pachyderm, Snakemake, and Airflow are merely designed for technical experts, and

182 the definition of workflows is done using high-level programming and scripting languages. To enable domain experts
183 to participate in the process, some tools provide a user-friendly interface to define workflows. However, they either
184 are made for a specific application domain (e.g., bioinformatics, computational chemistry, ecology, genomics, etc.)
185 or require some level of technical knowledge to manipulate the data. Thus, although most approaches and tools use
186 some form of DSL or UI, the abstraction level is not sufficient to allow for separation of concerns between definition
187 and implementation, which is necessary to effectively involve domain experts in workflow definition.

188 Another major challenge in Big Data workflows is the dynamic mapping workflow steps to heterogeneous com-
189 puting and storage resources to ensure scalability. This challenge comes from the fact that bottlenecks can occur on
190 an individual workflow step level, e.g., the throughput of one step is lower than others. Thus, scaling up the entire
191 workflow does not solve the scalability issues and needs to be done on the individual workflow step level. This issue
192 is exacerbated by the fact that the scalability needs to be organized and orchestrated over heterogeneous computing
193 resources. Achieving scalability in Big Data workflows has another dimension of challenges: exchanging data among
194 workflow components and race conditions when multiple instances of workflow components try to modify a shared
195 resource (e.g., a file) at the same time. Multiple workflow step instances can make up a large set of capabilities to
196 deliver the workflow's needs. Some approaches and tools discussed in the related work attempt to address this issue
197 through the use of containers and different types of middleware. However, no approach is able to unlock the full
198 potential for achieving step-level scalability of workflows, which relies on workflow and step encapsulation.

199 Finally, in Big Data workflows, data need to be passed between the workflow components so that the communi-
200 cation overhead is minimal. A communication solution must decouple the communication between the steps to be
201 scaled up while maintaining race-condition-free data access. Additionally, this communication module has to play a
202 central role in determining data flow between workflow steps. Based on our analysis of the state of the art, we find
203 there is no holistic Big Data workflow solution that can provide such a communication module along with high-level
204 workflow definition and scalable execution.

205 Accordingly we extracted the following requirements for our Big Data Workflow solution:

- 206 (a) a workflow definition mechanism with a clear separation between design- and run-time aspects and not limited
207 to a specific technology stack, application domain or ad-hoc processing models;
- 208 (b) a workflow run-time support that considers workflows as separate units, rather than as a single unit, for individ-
209 ual workflow steps; and
- 210 (c) a workflow enactment approach with event driven execution and support for race-condition-free parallel execu-
211 tion.

212 5. Proposed Solution

213 In this section, we propose an approach for the workflow step design and inter-step communication. For the
214 description of the Big Data Workflow we use the DSL from [24].

215 5.1. Overall Architecture

216 The solution enables various stakeholders to be involved in the creation of Big Data workflows. The desired
217 properties of the system are achieved by utilizing container and orchestration technologies and a DSL. The workflow
218 system is composed of three components: *Workflow Modelling Manager*, *Deployment Service Runtime*, and *Data*
219 *Storage/Sharing Ecosystem* (see Figure 1).

220 *The Workflow Modelling Manager* is the central element for defining workflow steps and composing them in
221 workflows. It comprises a set of tools and configurations that allow the formation of deployable Big Data workflows.
222 The component uses models that provide high-level descriptions of workflow steps and their dependencies. This com-
223 ponent handles storage configurations, data preparation, and step-level data processing and transformation operations.
224 The output of the component is a deployable data workflow. *The Deployment Service Runtime* is a component rep-
225 resenting the collection of hybrid computing resources where workflows steps are deployed. As individual workflow
226 steps are wrapped as containers, container orchestration tools play an important role in managing the heterogeneous
227 resources and allowing workflows step containers to be deployed. The component also controls operations such as

Figure 1: Overview of the our workflow system.

228 scaling and load balancing. *Data Storage/Sharing Ecosystem* is responsible for storing intermediate and output data
 229 and the data exchange mechanism during workflow execution. As workflow steps are deployed across heterogeneous
 230 distributed environments, the data exchange mechanism is an essential element that binds the workflow steps together
 231 by allowing them to pass data.

232 The system ensures the separation of design-time and run-time aspects of the workflows, i.e., workflow definition
 233 is done without considering the run-time execution. This allows having a separation of concerns among the involved
 234 stakeholders. Thereby, domain-experts can be responsible for extracting data processing requirements and structuring
 235 the high-level design of workflow steps. Technical experts provide the concrete programmatical implementations of
 236 the steps – for example, data scientists may provide workflow step-specific analytical models and data preparation
 237 code. Finally, DataOps experts are engaged in deploying and maintaining data workflows in production settings and
 238 monitoring data quality and related infrastructure status.

239 5.2. Big Data Workflow Description

240 The DSL used in this work [24] for representing Big Data workflows is inspired by [25] and is shown in Figure
 241 2. The domain conceptualised by the DSL is container-based Big Data workflows, which is reflected in the choice of
 242 concepts. The main concepts of the metamodel are used to represent the different aspects of the *Workflow Modeling*
 243 *Manager* element shown in Figure 1. *Workflow Step Definition* is implemented by the *Workflow* concept, which is
 244 comprised of a set of *Steps* in the DSL. Additionally, the element *Data Preparation and Storage Configuration* is im-
 245 plemented by the concepts *Parameter*, *Trigger* and *Communication Medium*, whereas the *Workflow Step Composition*
 246 element relates to the *Step Implementation* concept in the metamodel.

247 A *Workflow* is a sequence of steps that need to be executed in some order to process a set of data. It represents
 248 the conceptualized series of steps that perform different data ingestion, transformation, and analytics tasks. A given
 249 workflow can be defined by reusing another workflow. Besides the steps, a workflow is composed of a communication
 250 medium and a set of parameters. The *Steps* are the building blocks of a workflow, and each step corresponds to a
 251 single unit of data processing work in the workflow. The steps in a workflow are executed independently and are
 252 isolated from each other. Further, a step can have various options for its implementation and trigger mechanisms for
 253 executions.

254 A *Parameter* represents an input configuration value needed for the execution of a specific workflow instance. In
 255 addition to workflows, parameters can also be used to define configurations for workflow steps. The *Trigger* concept
 256 represents how the execution of a step instance is instantiated. In our metamodel, step execution can be triggered from
 257 a schedule that runs in a fixed interval of time, or it can be configured to run only once (e.g., during initialization of
 258 the workflow). Execution can also be triggered by an external event (e.g., invocation from a REST API or availability
 259 of input data in a message queue).

Figure 3: Components of workflow step template.

283 To enable the definition and deployment of workflow steps and their composition into a workflow, workflow steps
 284 are derived from a generic workflow step template supporting multiple programming languages. A workflow step
 285 can be prepared by customizing the generic template according to the need of the step and other settings. To achieve
 286 such flexibility, this template needs to be designed so that it is easy to introduce customization. The step template is
 287 composed of three main components: *Input Processing*, *Workflow Step Action*, and *Output Processing* (see Figure 3).

288 The *Input Processing* is responsible for handling incoming data; this includes fetching data from remote sources
 289 (e.g., copying or downloading a file from shared file volumes and moving the data to the step workspace, where it will
 290 be processed). Based on the step's configuration, input data can be fetched once at a container startup or scheduled
 291 to poll for the data availability at a specific time interval. The *Input Processing* can be triggered when a piece of data
 292 is available at the source. The *Workflow Step Action* is a wrapper component for step-specific data processing code.
 293 This component allows the injection of custom code using different programming languages. The data fetched by the
 294 *Input Processing* component is processed using the step-specific code in the step. The *Output Processing* component
 295 is responsible for delivering the processed data to a specific destination (e.g., upload to a remote source or move it
 296 to a shared volume for further processing by next steps) and notifying that the processed data is available for the
 297 next steps. *Output Processing* also includes the clearing up of temporary and input data from the step workspace.
 298 Configuration and attributes of a workflow step can be expressed as parameters and injected at the deployment time.
 299 The step parameters are accessible only by the corresponding step, but workflow-level parameters can be defined as
 300 well.

301 5.4. Inter-step Communication

302 The step design approach described in the previous section implements loose coupling of steps that comprise a
 303 workflow. However, in order to ensure that data between steps are transmitted consistently and correctly, consecutive
 304 steps need to communicate to notify each other of data availability. This communication corresponds to the *Fetch*
 305 *input data* and *Notify Next Steps* sub-processes of the *Input and Output processing* components in Figure 3. In the
 306 proposed workflow approach, MOM serves as a medium for workflow step communication. Two inter-dependent
 307 workflow steps communicate by passing data through MOM without direct interaction. The sender step pushes data
 308 to the MOM so that it is consumed by the receiver step at any time after the data becomes available in the MOM. The
 309 two steps do not need to run simultaneously for interaction, ensuring temporal decoupling. The space decoupling is
 310 also achieved since none of the sequential steps needs to know the other nor how many other steps are in the workflow.
 311 Since workflow steps are loosely coupled, they can be scaled independently. Therefore, it is possible to assign more
 312 instances to bottleneck workflow steps that are, for example, more computationally heavy and reduce the overall
 313 processing time.

Figure 4: Prototype Big Data workflow.

314 Specifically, message queues are used as a communication medium so that two inter-dependent workflow steps
 315 can share a queue to exchange data asynchronously. Both workflow step processes do not necessarily need to be
 316 running simultaneously to interact with the queue. Additionally, the messaging system is capable of providing an
 317 exactly-once message delivery guarantee. Furthermore, MOM-based communication ensures that the workflow does
 318 not run into race conditions. These can be seen in two scenarios:

- 319 • a workflow step that receives data does not access the data while the predecessor step is writing it. Message
 320 queues ensure that sending a message to a queue is independent of when it enters the queue and when the
 321 receiver reads it;
- 322 • and when a workflow step is scaled up, a step instance does not process a piece of data already being processed.
 323 This problem is avoided since a message is delivered to only a single step instance, i.e., data access is only for
 324 a specific instance.

325 The data patterns of the designed workflow are characterized according to the major workflow data patterns de-
 326 scribed in [27]. From a data visibility perspective, data elements are accessible from all workflow steps (e.g., data can
 327 be stored in shared file storage). Though a data element is accessible for all, it can only be used by a single workflow
 328 step instance at a time (e.g., when a reference of a file is transferred to the step from a message queue). Internally,
 329 data interaction happens only between two workflow step instances. Depending on the workflow step's purpose, it
 330 can also interact with an external source (e.g., by downloading a file from a remote source or invoking an external
 331 API endpoint). Data transfer is undertaken by the reference to the data element in some shared location (e.g., a file
 332 can be stored in a shared location, and its reference is exchanged over a message queue). In this case, data locking is
 333 not required; message queues restrict concurrent access to the data element. In terms of data-based routing, a given
 334 workflow step is executed whenever data are available at a network location.

335 6. Prototype Implementation

336 To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed solution, we developed a prototype Big Data workflow (see Figure
337 4) that implements the design choices described in Section 5 (available on GitHub¹³). The prototype workflow comes
338 from the domain of digital marketing (see [28] for a detailed description) and was chosen such that some of its steps
339 have higher compute requirements than others. Those steps need to be assigned with more computing resources than
340 other workflow steps to enable faster data processing. This makes it possible to demonstrate the applicability of step-
341 level scalability. The prototype workflow demonstrates the implementation of Big Data workflows using container
342 technology (encapsulating individual steps of the workflow), a messaging system (Message Queue), shared file system
343 volumes (can be local or distributed file system), and includes the following steps: (i) extract tab-separated values
344 (TSV) files from an archive file stored on a volume in a shared file system, (ii) convert TSV files to comma-separated
345 values (CSV) files, (iii) split CSV files into smaller pieces if the number of rows in the files is above a certain number,
346 (iv) clean and pre-process CSV files, (v) and convert tabular CSV files to JSON collections for further storage. The
347 DSL description of the prototype workflow is given in Listing 1.

348 6.1. Inter-step Communication

349 Asynchronous FIFO message queues are used to implement inter-step communication and the KubeMQ¹⁴ messag-
350 ing system was chosen for this purpose. KubeMQ provides multiple message queues with a guarantee of exactly-once
351 message delivery. A communication link is established when a workflow step is configured with a message queue as
352 its output channel, and the same queue is used as an input channel for another step. In this way, the latter step waits
353 for the output of the former and its execution is triggered immediately when the shared queues have content. This
354 communication mechanism enables the two step instances to run concurrently during execution while maintaining
355 race-condition-free data access. Such workflow execution follows the P&F architecture, i.e., step instances as filters
356 and message queues as pipes. In the example prototype, a containerized instance of KubeMQ is used to handle the
357 communication between the steps and is made accessible to all workflow steps. Each consecutive workflow step is
358 configured to share a message queue (except the first and last steps). Thereby, steps in the workflow use two message
359 queues: one for retrieving information about available input data from the previous step and one for signaling that
360 data have been made available for the next step. There is no direct link between two consecutive steps; instead, the
361 message queue they share creates a logical connection.

362 Even though the message queues in the prototype workflow serve as a communication mechanism, the actual data
363 for processing are not stored in the message queues but are stored on shared volumes. Only references to the data are
364 placed in the message queues. To organise the processing of the data, a step container allocates at least four different
365 file storage volumes: *in*, *work*, *out*, and *sandbox*. When a file reference becomes available in the input message queue
366 of a step container, it reads the file reference from the queue and accesses the file from its *in* volume. Then, the file is
367 moved to the *work* volume for processing. When file processing is completed, the result is stored in the *out* volume,
368 and the reference of the output file is published in the output message queue so that the next step can use it for further
369 processing. The *sandbox* volume is used to store any files that are not processed successfully.

370 6.2. Container Orchestration

371 The individual steps in a workflow are wrapped as Docker containers. The Docker images of the workflow steps
372 are derived from a generic step template that implements the input processing, output processing, and communication
373 logic. The template is modified by adding the installation script for any necessary software libraries in the Docker
374 image building configuration and injecting relevant code scripts (step processing code) in a specific place in the
375 template logic. Container orchestration systems provide effective means to deploy distributed applications across a
376 heterogeneous cluster of resources. To use these tools, it is necessary to prepare a deployment configuration file either
377 in JSON or YAML, which describes the location of the container images, network setups, and other configurations. In
378 the case of Big Data workflows, the configuration needs to include the description of different workflow steps and the
379 communication medium. Scalability and other constraints can also be stated in the configuration. When deploying a

¹³<https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/ebw-prototype>

¹⁴<https://kubemq.io>

```

workflow prototypeWorkflow {
  communicationMedium: medium MESSAGE_QUEUE
  parameters: MQ_HOST = kubemq
  steps:
    - step unzip
      triggers: external-event
      implementation:
        docker-implementation image: '/ebw-prototype-00-unzip'
      environment:
        STEP_NAME='00-unzip'

    - step tsv2csv
      triggers: external-event
      implementation:
        docker-implementation image: '/ebw-prototype-01-tsv2csv'
      environment:
        STEP_NAME='01-tsv2csv'

    - step split
      triggers: external-event
      implementation:
        docker-implementation image: '/ebw-prototype-02-split'
      environment:
        STEP_NAME='02-split'

    - step transform
      triggers: external-event
      implementation:
        docker-implementation image: 'ebw-prototype-03-transform'
        parameters: tranformationJar = '/transformation/transformation.jar'
      environment:
        STEP_NAME='03-transform'

    - step toarango
      triggers: external-event
      implementation:
        docker-implementation image: '/ebw-prototype-04-toarango'
        parameters: tranformationJson = '/transformation/transformation.json'
      environment:
        STEP_NAME='04-toarango' }

```

Listing 1: The DSL description of the prototype workflow.

380 workflow, the orchestration tool will automatically schedule the deployment of each workflow step to a cluster and
 381 pick the right host, taking into account any stated requirements or constraints.

382 The prototype workflow deployment was done by composing individual workflow step Docker containers using a
 383 Docker-compose file. A workflow step description in the file includes shared volumes, environment values, and mes-
 384 sage queue assignments. The communication medium, KubeMQ, is also included as a separate service in addition to
 385 the workflow steps. Rancher¹⁵ is used as an orchestration tool to deploy the workflow on a private cloud environment
 386 running Docker containers. In Rancher, the number of instances for each step can be defined in a separate YAML file.
 387 When this YAML file, together with the Docker compose file, is supplied, Rancher handles the deployment by taking
 388 the scalability requirement into account and finding the right host for each container.

389 6.3. Fault Tolerance

390 To address faults in Big Data workflows, it is necessary to keep track of each file's status while it is being pro-
 391 cessed. Having this information stored in a structured way helps for monitoring and debugging purposes. To this end,

¹⁵<https://rancher.com>

Table 2: Summary of feature-based comparison.

Workflow Tool	Step-level Containerisation	Communication Mechanism	DSL for Workflow
Airflow	Yes	Yes	No
Argo	Yes	No	Yes
Conductor	No	Yes	Yes
Nextflow	Yes	Yes	Yes
NiFi	No	Yes	No
Node-RED	No	No	No
Pachyderm	Yes	No	No
SnakeMake	Yes	No	Yes
<i>Our approach</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>

392 a centralized logging functionality writing structured logs in JSON format is incorporated. These logs are stored in
 393 scalable message queues, such as Kafka [29], and contain important execution statuses, warnings, and errors. A cen-
 394 tralized logging system can be a bottleneck when the system grows. This is because the logging unit gets overwhelmed
 395 by the flow of log data coming from scaled up workflow step instances. This slows down the overall performance
 396 of the workflow. However, our implementation is not significantly affected by this problem as the centralized log-
 397 ging approach is inspired by the state management system in well-known scalable platforms, such as Flink [30] and
 398 MillWheel [31]. In addition, the bottleneck on the logging mechanism can also be alleviated by using decentralized
 399 queueing systems. Errors in the common and step-specific scripts are handled differently by using a separate ex-
 400 ception handler. This is done by checking exit codes of program calls and operating system control flow constructs.
 401 Using such constructs, important program calls in the scripts are bound together with an error handler function. The
 402 error handler will be invoked when the program exits with an error code and logs error information, including the file
 403 causing the error, the line number that caused the error, and the input file’s name being processed.

404 To make the workflow more resilient to intermittent failures, we implemented retrying processing of failed input
 405 files. Whenever an error occurs, the input file is moved to the respective *sandbox* volume to be processed later or to
 406 be archived. Since the message queue implements exactly-once delivery, the reference of the file will not be available
 407 in the queue for retrials. In this case, all the failed files can be accessed directly from the sandbox without the need
 408 to access the message queue. When a step becomes free, i.e., when there are no more files in the message queue (or
 409 input directory for the first step), it tries to re-process files from the sandbox. With the current implementation, retrieval
 410 is done only once.

411 7. Evaluation

412 In this section, we present the evaluation of the proposed solution. It includes a feature-based comparison of the
 413 workflow solution against existing workflow tools and performance experiments based on the prototype implementa-
 414 tion.

415 7.1. Feature-based Comparison

416 To compare the proposed workflow solution with other similar tools, we selected three main implementation
 417 features: (i) the ability to wrap workflow steps as containers (isolated units); (ii) communication mechanism between
 418 steps and their activation trigger; and (iii) inclusion of DSL for workflow definition. (see Table 2).

419 Granular containerization (i.e., step-level containerization) is not provided out of the box for Big Data workflows
 420 containing multiple steps. Hence, step-level scalability cannot be achieved when faster processing is needed for an
 421 individual workflow step. Argo Workflows, Nextflow, Pachyderm, and SnakeMake are instances of the few Big Data
 422 workflow tools supporting step-level containerization. Nextflow also has an additional feature that allows deploying
 423 the entire workflow as a single container. The majority of existing data workflow tools lack such a separate commu-
 424 nication link and instead, steps in these tools are tightly coupled. Thereby, the logic that determines the flow of step

Figure 5: Results of the horizontal scalability test.

425 execution is embedded as part of the step implementation. Even though Argo Workflows provides both sequential and
 426 parallel workflow step definitions, this type of communication mechanism is missing.

427 Apache NiFi and Nextflow use a queuing system for inter-step communication. Nextflow provides advanced data
 428 binding and publish/subscribe features. Conductor has a special type of workflow step (i.e., event step) to enable event-
 429 based dependencies for steps by publishing events internally or an external message queuing system like Amazon
 430 SQS. Apache Airflow uses a feature called XCom to communicate small messages between steps and larger data are
 431 exchanged using remote storage such as S3 and HDFS. Defining workflows in existing data workflow tools requires
 432 knowledge of general-purpose programming and scripting languages such as Java, Python, Scala, or R. Consequently,
 433 domain-experts face a significant learning curve to master these languages. The need for DSLs is indispensable in this
 434 regard. Only a few Big Data workflow tools, e.g., Argo Workflows, Conductor, Nextflow, and SnakeMake, support a
 435 custom-made DSL for workflow definitions.

436 7.2. Performance Evaluation

437 We evaluated our workflow approach’s horizontal scalability using the prototype workflow and compared it with
 438 the Argo Workflows. We used eight heterogeneous physical hosts configured to form our distributed testbed. Three of
 439 them have 12-core Intel CPUs and 64 GB RAM each; the other five - four-core AMD CPUs and 16 GB RAM each.
 440 The hosts are connected in a Gigabit Ethernet network, share a distributed file system, and run the Docker engine
 441 connected to Rancher.

442 7.2.1. Scalability Evaluation

443 Our workflow solution allows us to scale individual workflow steps. Hence, it is worth investigating the impact
 444 of horizontal scalability on the performance of the workflow. Therefore, we designed an experiment to determine
 445 how the number of workflow step instances (i.e., containers) affects workflow execution performance. The prototype
 446 workflow, shown in Listing 1, was used for this experiment. We defined an increasing number of workflow step
 447 instances and measured the time it takes to complete processing input files. Input data size is kept constant over all
 448 iterations. The results of this experiment are shown in Figure 5.

449 We performed the scalability experiment by processing approximately 100 GB of compressed TSV files in nine
 450 rounds. These are historical data from the use case described in [28] that comprises a large volume of extracts
 451 from the Google Ads platform¹⁶ and made available for this experiment by a digital marketing company. For each
 452 round, we increased the number of workflow step instances by five (starting from 10), and the increased number was
 453 distributed among the steps based on the previous step execution time. Hence, the step that takes the longest time was

¹⁶<https://ads.google.com/home/>

454 allocated a higher number of instances. We stopped adding more step instances after nine rounds since we noticed
455 the minimal effect in the last two rounds. Figure 5 shows that with four times increase in the number of instances,
456 the total execution time decreases from 1,406 to 455 minutes, i.e., approximately a three-times decrease. There is a
457 significant reduction of execution time up to 20 containers. However, from 25 containers upwards, the reduction in
458 execution time gets smaller. This reduction in performance gains is due to resource bottlenecks with the addition of
459 more instances. In our experimental setup, resources available to the containers are shared. They are split among
460 the containers by availability time, size or processing power. Even though such an arrangement helps to utilize the
461 resources effectively, it can cause resource contention among the containers. As the number of instances increases, it
462 leads them to compete for the resources. Further increase of instances can result in degraded performance due to CPU,
463 memory, and I/O bottlenecks. Measuring the usage of such resources (CPU, memory, I/O, Network Receive/Transmit
464 Throughput, etc.) would be interesting but is considered out of scope for this evaluation as the container orchestration
465 system does not allow to easily change or customise them.

466 7.2.2. Comparison with Argo Workflows

467 The implemented workflow approach allows individual workflow steps to run independently. In this experiment,
468 we investigated the effect of concurrent workflow execution on the workflow’s performance by comparing our ap-
469 proach with another workflow tool that does not have built-in concurrency support. For the comparison, we chose
470 Argo Workflows since it does not have built-in concurrency support. The composition of a workflow can be done
471 quickly using its custom DSL that is similar to traditional YAML. Together with the step template invocator, the
472 container template was used to compose the sequential workflow with a single instance assigned for each step. The
473 experiment had two parts: one using fixed input data size, and the other is by using increasing input data size.

474 *Experiment with fixed input data size.* In this experiment, we compose workflows in both approaches and measure
475 the execution time of each step with a fixed volume of input data. We measure each the start and end time of each step
476 to observe the performance difference between concurrent and sequential execution modes. To achieve this, we used
477 the workflow in Listing 1 and followed the same workflow composition as in the scalability evaluation from Section
478 7.2.1, but with a single container instance assigned to each step. A similar workflow structure was composed in Argo
479 Workflows using the same step container images. Both workflows were executed using 100MB of input data on a
480 Kubernetes cluster (Argo Workflows runs only on Kubernetes). We measured the execution time for each step. To
481 minimize systematic errors, we repeated each experiment 20 times and took the arithmetic mean of execution time to
482 compare the two modes. The repetitions were done in a cool start fashion without caching result or intermediate data
483 from previous rounds.

484 The sequential execution mode in Argo Workflows takes 38.7 minutes to complete, whereas the concurrent mode
485 takes 34.6 minutes, which shows a slight performance gain when using our approach. Figure 6 (a), shows the execution
486 time for each step in Argo Workflows. Since the workflow is in sequential execution mode, step container execution
487 starts after the previous completes processing all the input files. In this mode, step containers are not initialized at
488 the time of workflow submission, and initialization occurs right before step execution, which results in a short gap in
489 between consecutive steps. The concurrent workflow execution based on our workflow implementation is shown in
490 Figure 6 (b). We observe a slight performance gain due to the concurrent execution of steps. Concurrency is enabled
491 by the P&F architectural design which allows workflow step container to continue processing the next input file
492 right after passing the processed file to the next step. Moreover, concurrent step containers share the host machine’s
493 resources, which explains the longer execution time of the last step (compared to sequential mode). Additionally, we
494 do not observe positive effects of the concurrency in the first three steps since their execution times are relatively short
495 (they are completed in a couple of minutes).

496 *Experiment with increasing input data size.* The previous experiment is repeated to evaluate which of the two work-
497 flow approaches performs better with increasing input data of compressed CSV files. To achieve this, we used the
498 workflow from Listing 1 once again and measured execution time for both approaches using input data starting from
499 0.1 up to 3 GB. Figure 7 shows the results of the experiment. It is evident from these results that our workflow ap-
500 proach performs better than Argo Workflows in all cases, with an approximate performance gain of 36%. However,
501 we did not observe a significant performance gain when input data are further increased. This is because the last two
502 steps are computationally intensive and they determine the overall speed of the workflow. Having a single container

Figure 6: Workflow execution times (a) using Argo Workflows and (b) using the proposed approach.

503 instance for each step, the addition of more input data does not bring any significant performance gain as the execution
 504 rate of steps is (relatively) constant independent of the size of the input data.

505 7.3. DSL Evaluation

506 We evaluated the proposed DSL qualitatively in what follows from a development and quality perspectives from
 507 multiple dimensions.

508 7.3.1. Development Perspective

509 One of the benefits of using DSL over general-purpose programming language is to reduce code complexity and
 510 increase development efficiency. However, it is challenging to measure the level of code abstraction introduced by
 511 using DSL. A simple quantitative evaluation metric can be used by measuring and comparing the amount of code
 512 required to define a workflow with and without DSL usage [32]. The measurement can be expressed in lines of code
 513 (LOC). Another metric is to compare the number of concepts or technologies involved with and without the DSL.
 514 This metric shows the number of concepts abstracted by the DSL.

515 For example, to implement the example workflow presented without using the DSL, it is necessary to follow
 516 some specific steps; however, the important work in this process is to compose all the workflow steps into a single
 517 deployment file. Then, assuming we have all the step images ready, it is required to set up the MOM and shared
 518 volumes. Also, input/output parameters, message queues, and environment variables must be adequately assigned for
 519 each workflow step. By using the DSL, composing a workflow requires fewer configurations since the DSL abstracts
 520 some concepts. For example, it is not required to set up MOM and assign message queues for workflow steps.

Figure 7: Performance with increasing input size.

521 Intermediate storage volumes and settings are not specified either. In other words, workflow definition using the DSL
 522 does not necessarily require knowing technologies like shared volume management, MOM, and message queues. To
 523 provide a quantitative comparison, we examined the LOC required to define workflow shown in Figure 4 with and
 524 without the DSL. Without using the DSL, the Docker compose file has 133 LOC¹⁷. Whereas the same workflow can
 525 only be expressed using 36 LOC by the DSL on a higher level of abstraction – see Listing 1. The DSL provides the
 526 capability to define the example workflow in a short LOC because of the abstraction of key concepts and technologies
 527 needed to define a workflow.

528 To test the functional ability of our DSL in the context of an IoT scenario, we mapped a third-party data preparation
 529 workflow used at Bosch as described in [33]. The mapping of the workflow to our approach is shown in Figure 8.
 530 The IoT scenario represents a use case at Bosch¹⁸ of quality monitoring for resistance spot welding. Data about the
 531 conducting of process are continuously generated at high velocity by sensors attached to the welding equipment and
 532 are managed by a welding software system. These data are stored in a database for and used by the software to signal
 533 for the current process status and potential issues. During the welding process, signals need to be generated at near-real
 534 time as any necessary response by the system or operators at the factory needs to be quickly addressed to avoid delays
 535 on the production lines. In addition to the sensor data from the welding machines, the use case involves reference data
 536 that provide information about target parameters of the equipment as well as the settings of the individual machines
 537 and welding programs. The overall goal of the work is to create a workflow for offline *batch* preparation of data for
 538 machine learning as well as online scenario for *real-time* monitoring using trained ML models.

539 The workflow consists of two parallel dependent sub-workflows that are involved in processing the different parts
 540 of the data. We use a grey shade to represent components specific to our approach that are necessary for the encapsu-
 541 lation of the workflow steps. Data transmission in this workflow and the rest of the examples in this section is done
 542 through shared file volumes of a (possibly distributed) file system, whereas the coordination of the steps (i.e., inform-
 543 ing the next step of available data for processing) is performed using a Message Queue that is dedicated for each pair
 544 of steps. The output of each step is passed by the *Output Processing (OP)* script to the *Input Processing (IP)* script of
 545 the next step, both of which are part of the wrapper of the respective images that wrap the step implementations. The

¹⁷<https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/ebw-prototype/blob/master/docker-compose.yml>

¹⁸<https://www.bosch.com/>

Figure 8: Mapping of approach to an IoT Big Data workflow about welding data preparation for machine learning.

546 left side of Figure 8 represents the sub-workflow for processing the reference datasets. In the first step, data are re-
 547 trieved from the meta settings and reference process curves databases and sent for further processing. The curves and
 548 metadata are integrated according to a common data model and are also re-formatted and prepared to be referenced by
 549 the larger scale sub-workflow. After the preparation data are stored in a reference database (implemented using Mongo-
 550 goDB¹⁹) where they can be accessed for lookups. The reference datasets are continuously but infrequently updated as
 551 new machine settings or reference data become available. The large-scale IoT data sub-workflow is displayed on
 552 the right side of Figure 8. This sub-workflow processes either very large volumes of historical welding quality and
 553 control data from a database (in the offline setting), or direct signals from the welding software system in real-time (in
 554 the online setting). The data retrieval step (numbered as step 4) fetches the data from the respective source and sends
 555 it to a dedicated slicing step. In the offline scenario, this step is used to chunk the data in a specific way, whereby
 556 the data coming from the software system is packaged together with the exact sensor data that relates to it in chunks
 557 of a pre-determined size (this correspondence is needed during the preparation step). The chunk size is calculated
 558 so that when the workflow is scaled, there are enough hardware resources (esp. RAM and CPU) to process them are
 559 available. The chunks are then sent for preparation during which the data are integrated, reformatted and packaged
 560 together with the specific relevant reference data through a lookup from a reference database. The result is then stored
 561 on disk for further training of or use by the machine learning models for welding quality prediction.

562 Another case study we tried to express in terms of our DSL is of the workflow *CloudFlows, A data mining*
 563 *workflow platform* [34]. Figure 9a shows a semantic triplet graph workflow built on the CloudFlows framework from
 564 an RSS feed workflow.

565 The first step of the workflow implements an RSS Reader that takes an RSS feed URL as input. The second step
 566 summarizes news articles based on the generated read data from the first step. The text from the news feed is then
 567 passed to the next step of the workflow that performs triplet extraction. This step implements NLP techniques to

¹⁹<https://www.mongodb.com/>

Figure 9: Mapping of approach to existing Big Data workflows - (a) CloudFlows data mining and (b) ENCODE Data access workflows.

568 extract *subject-verb-object* triples from the news articles. Step four of the workflow uses a WordNet²⁰ Lemmatizer
 569 on the resulting triples, and step five performs a sliding window that takes the number of triplets as input. Finally, the
 570 data window is passed to the Streaming triplet graph, which is the last step of this workflow.

571 Another case study is of *ENCODE Data Access* [35] shown in Figure 9b. In the first step of the workflow, the
 572 user enters a REST-format ENCODE query or uploads an ENCODE metadata file that represents a dataset array
 573 corresponding to the so-called *bags* of data. The selected data are then transferred for analysis to the DNase-seq
 574 sub-workflow that implements a set of analyses on the data. After the analysis is performed, the result (also serialized
 575 into bags) is published on Amazon S3, and a metadata file (named “fetch.txt”) is created and stored for serving to
 576 the users of the result. A user may then discover these new bags and perform further analysis using the same type of
 577 querying as in step 1, but with another analysis set.

578 7.3.2. Quality Characteristics

579 We used the Framework for Qualitative Assessment of DSLs (FQAD) [36] that defines sets of quality character-
 580 istics to evaluate DSLs. The quality characteristics are mainly determined from ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard but
 581 tailored for DSLs.

582 FQAD is helpful for evaluating the requisite quality characteristics at the outset of DSL development, as well as
 583 assessing the end product of the DSL development process (i.e., the language). It defines a set of assessment goals
 584 and DSL characteristics to fulfill them, which are derived from the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 international systems and
 585 software standards model.

²⁰<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

586 Several researchers used this framework to evaluate their DSL. For example, Florian et al [37] used this framework
587 to evaluate a DSL in the business domain language for creating test case specification. Furthermore, Aleksandar et al
588 [38] employed this framework to do quality assessment of their DSL for modeling application-specific functionalities
589 of business applications.

590 Below, we outline these characteristics and assess the developed DSL based on them.

- 591 • **Functional suitability:** This refers to the degree to which a DSL is completely developed. Functional suitability
592 further has two sub-characteristics:
 - 593 – **Completeness:** The ability of a DSL to express all concepts and scenarios of the domain is termed as
594 completeness. We successfully implemented four different workflows with our DSL. The language was
595 expressive enough to describe the workflows efficiently.
 - 596 – **Appropriateness:** The scale to which the DSL is appropriate for the particular applications of the domain
597 is called appropriateness. While implementing the Encode workflow, we faced the challenge of incorpo-
598 rating all elements in one workflow. However, by breaking it down into two separate workflows based
599 on the functionality and with additional REST services, we achieved the required functionality with our
600 DSL.

601 The functional suitability analysis shows that all the important functionality is included in the DSL. In other
602 words, the DSL should not contain functionalities that are not part of the domain. In this regard, based on the
603 workflows that were mapped to our DSL, we claim that the DSL implemented in this work covers the core
604 functionality required to define a given data workflow.

- 605 • **Usability:** This aspect refers to the degree to which a group of users can use a DSL to achieve specific goals.
606 A DSL must be as simple as possible to express the domain concepts and support its users. As presented, our
607 DSL provides the option to define concise workflows with minimal technical knowledge.
- 608 • **Reliability:** It defines the characteristics of the language that help to produce reliable code. This includes func-
609 tionalities to prevent errors and support for model checking. The DSL was implemented using the Eclipse
610 environment that supports languages designed with precise semantics based on well-defined principles. Addi-
611 tionally, the Eclipse IDE also has essential features to debug and handle code errors. The reliability character-
612 istics has two sub-characteristics:
 - 613 – **Model Checking:** This concerns whether the DSL reduces user error rates. In comparison to writing
614 YAML scripts, our DSL-based approach has a very low error rate.
 - 615 – **Correctness:** The term correctness concerns whether appropriate elements, as well as the correct relation
616 between them, are provided, i.e., any unexpected interactions are prevented. We use a message queue
617 as the communication medium for different elements/steps of the workflow to communicate. This makes
618 sure that there is no unexpected interaction between the elements.
- 619 • **Maintainability:** This characteristic refers to the degree to which it is easy to maintain a DSL. A DSL needs to
620 be easy to modify or introduce new concepts. Modularity falls under this characteristic as well. The DSL was
621 designed based on the separation of concerns principle. This makes it easily understandable and maintainable.
 - 622 – **Modifiability:** This characteristic refers to the DSL's ability to incorporate new functionality by as little
623 modification as possible. The modular approach of our DSL makes it easier to add new vocabulary that
624 can be used to describe Big data workflows.
 - 625 – **Low coupling:** This means how discrete the elements of the DSL are. At this stage, each element of the
626 DSL plays an integral part in describing a workflow. Therefore, the change in each element will have an
627 impact on other elements.
- 628 • **Productivity:** This is mainly related to the number of resources required by a user to achieve specific goals.
629 Productivity can be improved using our DSL because of two main reasons. First, the DSL incorporates high-
630 level concepts of Big Data workflows. Hence, designing a workflow using the DSL is simplified and can be done

631 quickly. Second, the language provides automatic generation of template workflow code and configurations.
632 This saves a lot of time compared to when the process is done manually from scratch.

- 633 • **Extensibility:** This characteristic expresses the degree to which a language has mechanisms for users to add new
634 features. The language we have presented currently has a low degree of extensibility since it does not provide
635 users a means to extend the language with new functionalities.
- 636 • **Compatibility:** This characteristic measures degrees to which a DSL is compatible with the domain and devel-
637 opment process. Our DSL was developed iteratively, in different stages and modified to cover concepts relevant
638 in the domain.
- 639 • **Expressiveness:** Expressiveness is defined as the degree to which a problem-solving strategy can naturally be
640 mapped into a DSL program. The DSL was developed after a thorough domain analysis in which each concept
641 has mapped to its corresponding metamodels to represent core elements and does not cover complex structures
642 such as cyclic workflows. The sub-characteristics of the expressiveness are as follows:
 - 643 – **Mind to program mapping:** Concepts are designed appropriately and named so that they are intuitive in
644 order to accommodate problem-solving tasks for the domain.
 - 645 – **Uniqueness:** Because of its simplicity, our DSL provides one and only one good way to express every
646 concept of interest.
 - 647 – **Orthogonality:** Each construct in our Big Data workflow DSL is used to represent exactly one distinct
648 concept in the domain.
 - 649 – **Correspondence to important domain concepts:** DSL constructs correspond to important domain concepts
650 and the language does not include trivial domain concepts. Our DSL only includes highly relevant and
651 non-trivial Big Data workflow concepts.
 - 652 – **Conflicting elements:** This refers to the absence of conflicts between the DSL elements. Our DSL concepts
653 have no conflicts as each element serves a unique purpose for data workflows specification.
 - 654 – **Right abstraction level:** This refers to whether the DSL is at the correct abstraction level that it is not more
655 complex or detailed than necessary. Our DSL provides only the highly important elements of the domain
656 at the moment. A few more elements are planned to be added to enhance the functionality– for example,
657 concepts for aspects of data transmission.
- 658 • **Reusability:** This characteristic refers to how a language construct can be used in more than one language. The
659 grammar specification of our DSL can be imported and reused in the Eclipse environment. Furthermore, the
660 language is conceptualized so that some elements can be reused in the workflow definition. For example, a
661 workflow element from one workflow can be used to define another workflow.
- 662 • **Integrability:** This characteristic measures how a DSL can be integrated with other languages and modeling
663 tools. The DSL that we have provided can be exported as a plug-in within the Eclipse environment. The ex-
664 ported plug-in can then be imported into another language project using the Eclipse platform’s built-in features.

665 **8. Conclusions**

666 In this article, we described a Big Data workflow approach that allows specification of Big Data workflows at a
667 high level of abstraction and enables separation of design- and run-time aspects while maintaining scalable workflow
668 execution. Scalable workflow execution entails parallel data processing that requires workflow fragments to run
669 separately on different computing resources. In the future, we plan to implement comprehensive provenance support.
670 Another limitation to be addressed is the use of a centralized message-oriented communication, which could become a
671 bottleneck for large-scale execution and is a single point failure. Decentralized communication media, Web services,
672 or distributed file systems can potentially be used to address this issue. The DSL that is used in this work is limited
673 to expressing core workflow structures. Thus, the experiments on scalable workflow execution for an extended DSL
674 with different workflow structures can be performed. Finally, a visual language for workflow definition, composition,
675 and run-time monitoring would be essential to support domain-experts’ participation in workflow design.

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